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Russia's Challenge to NATO's Enlargement Policy: A Critical Analysis of the Ukraine Conflict

Suheel Ahmad Parry

Abstract

This paper explores the ongoing war between Russia and Ukraine critically, using it as a case study to demonstrate the major challenges that Russia poses to NATO's enlargement policy. The complicated interplay between the conflict's escalation and NATO's continuous desire for expansion is at the centre of this paper. The study begins by shedding light on how NATO's enlargement programme, purportedly intended to foster peace and security, has negligently become a fuel for geopolitical turmoil in Europe. The developing crisis in Ukraine is a dramatic illustration of the tensions that have arisen as a result of NATO's expansion plans, with Russia viewing these moves as direct threats to its national security. By delving into the complexities of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, this article thoroughly dissects Russia's passionate opposition to NATO's expanding reach. It investigates the fundamental motivations and strategic factors motivating Russia's resistance, offering insight into the broader consequences for European stability and international relations.

Introduction

The geopolitical landscape of the 21st century has been marked by a series of complex challenges, none more significant than the ongoing tension between Russia and Ukraine. Central to this dynamic is NATO's policy of enlargement, a strategy aimed at incorporating new member states into the alliance. The post-Cold War period has been marked by considerable instability, characterized by numerous crises between NATO and Russia. These tensions arose due to NATO's enlargement, the Kosovo war, Western support for colour revolutions, the U.S.-backed missile shield, and other factors. Over the past two decades since the fall of the Berlin Wall and the dissolution of the Soviet Union, interactions between NATO and Russia have fostered a profound

sense of mistrust on both sides. Both NATO and Moscow exhibit a common trait: the pursuit of proactive foreign policies. NATO has demonstrated its proactivity through membership expansion, military operations, and diversification of its activities. Concurrently, under Putin's leadership, Moscow has pursued an assertive foreign policy, aiming to weaken Western unity and enhance Russian power and regional sway. For both entities, taking action is crucial for asserting their existence and influence (Kanet and Larive 2012, 76).

These divergent interpretations extend beyond mere rhetoric or verbal disputes. The tensions between Russia and NATO carry tangible consequences for stability in Europe. Hence, this paper delves into the heart of this intricate relationship, focusing specifically on the critical lens of the Ukraine conflict. The conflict in Ukraine, which unfolded against the backdrop of NATO's enlargement efforts, has intensified the longstanding rivalry between Russia and the Western alliance. It is crucial to assess whether NATO's expansion contributed to the Ukraine crisis and to explore potential future enlargement strategies. This study undertakes a comprehensive analysis, scrutinizing the motivations, implications, and consequences of NATO's expansion policy in the context of the Ukraine conflict. By examining the historical antecedents, the evolution of NATO's policy, and the events leading up to the Ukraine crisis, this research aims to unravel the complex interplay of geopolitics, security concerns, and national interests. As we delve into this critical analysis, we explore the multifaceted dimensions of the conflict, shedding light on the strategic calculations and ideological clashes that have defined Russia's challenge to NATO's enlargement policy. Through this examination, we seek not only to understand the past but also to illuminate potential pathways for future diplomatic engagement, offering insights crucial for policymakers and scholars alike in navigating the intricate geopolitics of the 21st century.

NATO and its enlargement policy

NATO, the North Atlantic Treaty Organization, is an international military alliance comprising 31 member states from both Europe and North America. Its official establishment took place with the signing of the North Atlantic Treaty on April 4, 1949. The composition of NATO has significantly transformed since its inception. Initially formed by the original 12 founding nations, the alliance

experienced expansion during the Cold War period, welcoming, West Germany, Greece, Spain and Turkey into its fold. The reunification of Germany in 1990 led to the incorporation of East Germany into NATO's territory. Following the end of the Cold War, NATO entered a notable phase of enlargement. After the Cold War ended, NATO underwent a remarkable phase of enlargement, integrating Eastern European countries such as the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland in 1999, followed by Bulgaria, Romania, Latvia, Estonia, Lithuania, Slovakia, and Slovenia in 2004. Further additions included Croatia and Albania (2009), Montenegro (2017), North Macedonia (2020), and most recently, Finland in 2023.¹ NATO's procedure for admitting new members is outlined in Article 10 of the treaty. According to this article, any European state can join NATO if all existing member countries unanimously agree to its membership. The procedure entails the invited state submitting its accession document to the Government of the United States. Once this step is completed, the U.S. government informs all NATO parties about the successful accession. This meticulous process underscores the significance of mutual consent among member states.²

Significance of NATO's enlargement policy

The Study on Expansion approved by the NATO Council in September 1995 observed that the enlargement of NATO should “complement the enlargement of the EU, a parallel process which also ... contributes significantly to extending security and stability to the new democracies of the East”, and that “NATO's enlargement must be understood as only one important element of a broad European security architecture that transcends and renders obsolete the idea of “dividing lines” in Europe” (Forster and Wallace 2001, 14). NATO's pursuit of increasing its membership is rooted in its core objective of fostering collective security and stability among nations. The development of NATO's policy on enlargement naturally progressed throughout the 1990s. Within the alliance, intense debates occurred about the advantages and disadvantages of broadening its membership. Supporters argued that expanding NATO would aid the transformation of ex-communist nations into democracies, address security issues in central and eastern Europe, and establish a unified security structure across the continent (Asmus, Kugler, & Larrabee, 1993; Talbott, 1995).

NATO officials argued that expansion not only promoted democracy and stability but also improved the alliance's capacity to combat terrorism. At the 2002 Prague summit, US President George W. Bush emphasised the importance of NATO enlargement. He emphasized that “each new member brought valuable military capabilities to enhance collective security”. This was evident in Afghanistan, where troops from Bulgaria, Romania, Estonia, Slovakia and Lithuania, as well as 16 NATO allies, worked together to confront global terrorism (George W. Bush, 2002). This argument underscores the strategic importance of NATO's enlargement, showcasing how new members contributed effectively to joint efforts in addressing contemporary security challenges.

On the other side, sceptics contended that NATO was no more necessary for Europe's security after the end of the Soviet Union. They felt adding former communist nations was expensive and could provoke Russia, making enlargement risky (Mandelbaum 1995, 11; Art1998,385). NATO leaders yielded to pressures to assist former communist countries, expanding the organization beyond its initial mutual defence scope. Concurrently, a growing sense of Western mistrust of Russia emerged in the enlargement decision-making process. (Ivanov, 2011). A significant decision made by NATO was that Russia would not have veto power over any decisions on enlargement, establishing an expanded European security framework that would exclude Russia from its primary decision-making procedures (NATO, 1995).³ This development underscored the evolving dynamics of NATO's relationship with Russia, indicating a shift towards a security framework that limited Russia's influence in the region.

Russia as a challenge to NATO's enlargement policy

The challenge posed by Russia to NATO's enlargement policy can be traced back to the early 1990s. Even before NATO openly discussed its enlargement policy, the Russian government, led by Boris Yeltsin, perceived the alliance's eastward expansion as a direct threat to Russia's national interests (Sergounin 1997, 61-62). This apprehension intensified when NATO formally initiated a study on enlargement in late 1994. Russian opposition to this idea became vehemently vocal. President Yeltsin strongly opposed NATO expansion during the Commission for Security and Cooperation in Europe session in Budapest in December 1994. He criticised the approach harshly,

saying that it put Europe in danger by causing it to pursue a "cold peace." (Sciolino 1994). This event marked a pivotal moment when Russia openly challenged NATO's expansion plans, setting the stage for ongoing tensions between the two entities. Russia's opposition to enlargement remained well into the middle of the 1990s and only subsided once the Permanent Joint Council was established, as described in the May 1997 Founding Act. Despite the fact that this action cleared the way for NATO's initial eastward expansion, which included the Poland, Czech Republic and Hungary in 1999, Russia remained sceptical about the expansion regardless of its formal connection. However, Russia made it clear in February 1999 that any further NATO expansion would be seen as crossing a "red line" (Maitra 2021, 39).

Russia believes that NATO's expansion toward its borders signifies the West's attempt to increase its influence while weakening Russian power. For instance, Sergei Karaganov articulates that NATO's expansion represents an extension of its influence, particularly in critical military and political domains. Despite this, the West's determination in enlarging NATO contrasts sharply with its refusal to acknowledge Russia's right to its sphere of influence. According to Karaganov, this position has prevented the end of the Cold War. Even though there are no longer any ideological or military confrontations, the geopolitical rivalry that dominated that time has returned to the fore in the world's most important international relations (Karaganov, 2016). According to Russia's geopolitical perspective, NATO expansion would be acceptable if NATO transitions into a primarily political organization with a reduced military focus. To achieve this, the West must involve Russia in ensuring Europe's security. This involvement could happen either through Russia becoming a full member of NATO or by establishing a new European collective security mechanism (Diesen & Wood 2012, 455).

The expansion of NATO's membership, conducted without involving Russia in the decision-making process, not only raised concerns but became an important cause of Russia's aggression towards neighbouring states. This anxiety increased as a result of NATO's substantial military presence in Europe, its 1999 military intervention in Serbia, which was pro-Russian, its support for democratic uprisings in Ukraine and Georgia, its recognition of Kosovo's independence without Russian consent in 2008, and the idea of a European missile defence system (Allison 2014,

1271). In reaction to the probable NATO offer of a Membership Action Plan (MAP) to Georgia and Ukraine, Russia stepped up its resistance to enlargement. When NATO leaders gathered in Bucharest in 2008, Putin issued a grave warning: "We view the appearance of a powerful military bloc on our borders... as a direct threat to the security of our country."⁴ There have been increased tensions between Russia and Georgia as a result of these developments in NATO's enlargement policy, particularly the possibility of granting Georgia a Membership Action Plan (MAP). The war between Russia and Georgia in 2008 effectively stalled Georgia's NATO aspirations. This conflict highlighted the security concerns arising from NATO's expansion near Russian borders. Subsequently, in 2014, Russia's annexation of Crimea occurred amidst the ongoing Ukraine conflict, viewed by Russia as a response to NATO's enlargement policy. This study will delve into the evolving Russia-Ukraine conflict, contextualizing it within the backdrop of NATO's enlargement and its implications on regional security dynamics.

NATO's Expansion and the Russia-Ukraine Conflict: unravelling the connections

The origins of the conflict in Ukraine can be attributed to the country's ambitions to align itself with Western organizations such as the EU and NATO. Following the Soviet Union's dissolution, Ukraine's efforts to establish closer ties with the West have faced opposition from Russia (Kudors and Pabriks 2016, 68). Ukraine established official ties with NATO in 1992 following its independence and subsequent membership in the North Atlantic Cooperation Council. However, significant advancements in these relations were made during Viktor Yushchenko's presidency. (2005–2010). Viktor Yushchenko restored Ukraine's strategic objective of "full membership in NATO and the European Union" in the military policy of the nation in April 2005.⁵ Although, these aspirations of both Ukraine and Georgia to join NATO in 2008 were thwarted by Russia's invasion of Georgia, underscoring the complex geopolitical challenges faced by nations seeking closer integration with Western alliances (Khan 2008, 1-14). This Russian invasion of Georgia marked a first aggressive challenge for NATO's enlargement policy, posing significant implications not only for Georgia but also for Ukraine.

However, President Yanukovich's pursuit of closer relations with NATO, despite Russia's invasion of Georgia, underscores the complexities of Ukraine's foreign policy decisions during his second term. He emphasised “the value of Ukraine's alliance with NATO in 2010, claiming that despite Ukraine's lack of readiness to enlist, the vast nation could not survive without this cooperation” (Yanukovich, 2010). Ukrainian Prime Minister Yatsenyuk announced in August 2014 that he intended to ask parliament to approve Ukraine's membership in NATO. The following month, President Petro Poroshenko took part in the NATO summit in Wales and made announcements regarding the willingness of certain NATO members to provide lethal military support to Ukraine. Following the summit, President Poroshenko spoke before the U.S. Congress, pleading for Washington to grant Ukraine "special" security status, signifying the highest degree of cooperation with a non-NATO partner (Poroshenko 2014).

During Yanukovich's presidency, Ukraine and NATO maintained active collaboration, conducting joint seminars, tactical exercises, and strategic operations. Despite Ukraine's non-membership status, this cooperation raised concerns in Russia, viewing it as a potential threat to its security. The intensification of Ukraine's relationship with NATO, marked by joint military activities, exacerbated tensions. The Kremlin perceived these interactions as a direct challenge, prompting a forceful response. Russia's aggressive actions, notably the invasion and annexation of Crimea, can be seen as a manifestation of its deep-seated concerns about NATO's expanding influence in its vicinity.

The Russian annexation of Crimea in 2014, leaving the country in a state of heightened vulnerability. Faced with this blatant act of aggression, Ukraine sought increased support from Western allies, particularly NATO, to bolster its security and deter future Russian aggression. From 2014 to 2019, Ukraine made significant strides in strengthening its ties with NATO, marking a period of intensified cooperation and strategic alignment. A coordinated effort to improve Ukraine's military capabilities was announced in 2015 by joint military drills between NATO nations and Ukraine, including Operation Fearless Guardian, which included 2,200 participants (Weisman, 2015). The Verkhovna Rada, Ukraine's parliament, underscored its commitment to NATO integration by passing a law on June 8, 2017, prioritizing this integration as a foreign policy

objective.⁶ Following that, NATO formally added Ukraine to its list of prospective members on March 10, 2018, recognising the nation's commitment to the alliance. On September 20, 2018, the Ukrainian parliament passed modifications to the constitution that made NATO and EU membership the country's main foreign policy goals. On February 7, 2019, the parliament passed a constitutional amendment by an overwhelming margin, further solidifying Ukraine's determination to join the European Union and the North Atlantic Alliance (Pifer, 2000, pp.50-53). These events emphasised Ukraine's strong commitment to joining NATO and marked a pivotal time in its quest for Euro-Atlantic integration and improved security cooperation.

Ukraine's aspirations for NATO membership have accelerated since President Volodymyr Zelenskyy took office in May 2019. Ukraine enrolled in NATO's enhanced opportunity partner interoperability programme in June 2020, a move that suggested a desire for stronger ties with the organisation but did not ensure immediate membership. The National Security Strategy of Ukraine, which emphasises NATO membership, was updated by Zelenskyy's administration to reaffirm its commitment to NATO integration. Zelenskyy emphasised the significance of achieving a NATO Membership Action Plan (MAP) for Ukraine's security and defence during a meeting with British Prime Minister Boris Johnson in October 2020 (Zelenskyy, 2020). In response Secretary-General Stoltenberg emphasized that "Russia does not have the authority to veto Ukraine's accession to NATO".⁷ These developments of Zelenskyy highlighted Ukraine's increasing closeness to joining NATO. However, in February 2022, Russia launched a full-scale invasion of Ukraine, indicating the escalating tension and aggression between the two nations. Russia's occupation of Ukraine is a complex issue, rooted in historical, cultural, and geopolitical factors. However, Russia's main worry is on the substantial security risk it sees if Ukraine were to become a full member of NATO and use Article 5's collective defence clause. Article 5 of the NATO treaty states: "The Parties agree that an armed attack on one or more of them in Europe or North America is an attack on all. They will assist the attacked Party or Parties with necessary actions, including armed force, to restore and maintain security in the North Atlantic area."⁸

Russia's aggressive actions in the context of the Russia-Ukraine conflict can be directly attributed to NATO's enlargement policy. The expansion of NATO membership, coupled with its

military presence and interventions in neighbouring regions, triggered alarm in Russia. George Kennan would undoubtedly have recognised Putin's response. Author of the "containment" strategy against the Soviet Union, Kennan declared in 1997 that "expanding NATO would be the most fateful error of American policy in the entire post-Cold War era." "Such a decision may be expected to inflame the nationalistic, anti-Western, and militaristic tendencies in Russian opinion, to have a negative impact on the advancement of Russian democracy, to revive the Cold War atmosphere in East-West relations, and to push Russian foreign policy in directions decidedly against our wishes," Kennan continued (cited in Moskowitz, 2022).” The Russia-Ukraine conflict is seen as a response to prevent Ukraine from joining NATO, underscoring Russia's strategic moves to safeguard its interests in the face of perceived threats emanating from NATO's expansion policy.

Conclusion

In the wake of the critical analysis of the Ukraine conflict within the context of NATO's enlargement policy, it becomes evident that the geopolitical chessboard of Europe remains a complex terrain, marked by persistent tensions and potential flashpoints. The case of Ukraine has not only revealed the deep-seated animosities between Russia and the Western alliance but also highlighted the intricate interplay of historical grievances, national interests, and regional security dynamics. NATO's steadfast commitment to its enlargement policy, exemplified by recent developments such as Finland's membership, underscores the alliance's enduring vision of a Europe united under its protective umbrella. However, this ambition carries profound implications. The open-door policy of NATO, while rooted in transformative ideals, has thus far failed to engender trust and cooperation with Russia. Instead, it has acted as a catalyst for hostility, leading to periodic episodes of conflict, such as witnessed in Ukraine.

In the foreseeable future, adhering to NATO's ongoing policy of enlargement as usual could sustain instability in Europe, maintaining the threat of Russian hostility and the possibility of military conflicts. While NATO's ambitions are admirable, they require a careful reassessment, taking into account the intricate geopolitical landscape. Moving forward, diplomatic efforts should

prioritize open dialogue, compromise, and sincere attempts to address shared concerns. By adopting such prudent approaches, the alliance can aim to mend divisions and create a more secure, steady, and collaborative European future.

Notes and References

¹ As of the joining of Finland, NATO's membership currently stands at 31 countries. See. "NATO Member Countries," NATO, last modified June 8, 2023. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_52044.htm.

² Under Article 10 of the North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO), the eligibility criteria for adding new members to the alliance are outlined. This article serves as the foundational framework guiding the accession process, emphasizing the principles of democracy, individual liberty, and the rule of law. For more details see.. "Enlargement and Article 10," NATO, last modified August 3, 2023, https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_49212.htm.

³NATO. "Study on NATO Enlargement (Ch. 2.C.27)." September 3, 1995. http://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/official_texts_24733.htm.

⁴ Vladimir Putin, 'Remarks by Russian President Vladimir Putin at NATO Bucharest summit press conference', 4 April 2008, <http://en.kremlin.ru/events/president/transcripts/24903>.

⁵ BBC News. "Medvedev warns on NATO expansion." March 25, 2008. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/europe/7312045.stm>.

⁶ Interfax Ukraine. "Rada Restores Ukraine's Course for NATO Membership as Foreign Policy Priority." *Interfax Ukraine*, June 8, 2017. <https://en.interfax.com.ua/news/general/427216.html>.

⁷ NATO Secretary General: It's Not Russia's Decision Whether Ukraine Will Be a Member of the Alliance. (2021, June 14). Eurointegration. <https://www.eurointegration.com.ua/news/2021/06/14/7124429/>

⁸ North Atlantic Treaty Organization. (n.d.). Article 5 - Collective defence clause. *NATO Official Website*. https://www.nato.int/cps/en/natohq/topics_110496.htm

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Author

Suheel Ahmad Parry (Senior Research Fellow, Department of Political Science, University of Kashmir)